

Do We Need a Classifier? Dual Objectives Go Beyond Baselines in Fine-Grained Emotion Classification

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Abstract

Fine-grained emotion classification refers to the task of identifying and distinguishing among a large number of subtle emotional states with nuanced differences. The classification scope extends substantially beyond coarse-grained categories, such as broad valence (e.g., positive, negative) or limited basic emotion taxonomies (e.g., Ekman [3], Plutchik [4]). The standard approach today for this classification task involves fine-tuning a pre-trained language model (e.g., BERT) with a classifier head, using a standard cross-entropy loss. In this work, we revisit the foundations of emotion modeling and propose a novel alternative approach to fine-grained emotion recognition from text. We reframe this multi-label classification as a semantic similarity estimation with a contrastive objective between the text and emotion labels, and develop our model without employing any classifier head. This model, trained with the mentioned approach, is found to surpass several existing baseline models on fine-grained emotion detection benchmarks. Building on this insight, we introduce a dual-objective framework that jointly optimizes similarity alignment along with a classification objective, which enables a better understanding of emotional semantics and effective handling of class imbalance. Our experiments demonstrate that the proposed formulation yields consistent performance improvements and achieves state-of-the-art performance among existing baselines, with macro-F1 scores of 0.56 on GoEmotions and 0.61 on SemEval-2018 Task-1C. Additionally, we evaluate our approach on the EmoPillars dataset, demonstrating the robustness and generalizability of the proposed methods across multiple datasets.

1 Introduction

Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become an integral part of our daily lives. Understanding human emotions has long been a central challenge in AI.

GoEmotions	Label(s)
Thanks! I love watching him every week	gratitude, love
[NAME] was bottom 3 just last split...	neutral
EmoPillars	Label(s)
The pope is coming to Fıtima again? I didn't expect that.	surprise
I need to find a way to save Padm. I can't lose her.	desire, fear, sadness
SemEval-2018 1C	Label(s)
Your future is bright. Remember	joy, optimism
This is awful	disgust

TABLE I: Examples from our datasets used

From education [5], and marketing [6] to conversational agents [7] and content moderation, modern digital environments increasingly demand systems that can interpret subtle, fine-grained emotional cues expressed in natural language. Although humans effortlessly infer such affective states using context, world knowledge, and implicit associations, enabling machines to do the same remains a difficult problem in natural language understanding (NLU). Emotions are nuanced, subjective, multi-label in nature, and often sparsely expressed—making them fundamentally more complex than traditional categorical NLP tasks such as sentiment analysis or topic classification. In recent years, with the development of large transformer-based [1] pre-trained language models such as BERT [2], RoBERTa [8], and the availability of several datasets, significant advancements have been made in understanding emotions from human languages. However, detecting fine-grained subtle emotions in text remains a complex issue in NLP with numerous practical applications, such as mental health counselling [9], social media analysis [10], [11], human-computer interaction [12], and much more. Fine-grained classification tasks are challenging precisely due to the presence of class interference among closely confusable emotion classes [13], and complexity increases many times as the number of classes increases. Despite the significant

improvements achieved by the standard finetuning of these pretrained models, fine-grained emotion classification still faces two primary obstacles: (a) Multi-label emotion datasets available are highly imbalanced. Frequent emotions dominate, while some appear rarely, and so the standard with cross-entropy loss tends to bias models toward the majority classes, reducing overall performance. (b) Classical supervised training relies solely on the discrete label identifiers, and as a result, the model often captures task-specific patterns but lacks deeper alignment with conceptual emotional semantics. The model fails to understand the actual meaning of emotions, the correlations between emotion labels, and to separate emotions having nuanced differences.

In this work, we focus on the objective design for fine-grained emotion classification and show that strong performance can be achieved without architectural complexity, large models, or heavy computation. We introduce a temperature-scaled contrastive loss, NT-BiXent, which leverages semantic label definitions for multi-label similarity learning without requiring a classifier head. Furthermore, we propose a dual-objective framework that combines our NT-BiXent loss and the Clipped Asymmetric Loss [14]. We conduct extensive experiments leveraging RoBERTa-base as the encoder backbone across multiple benchmark datasets: GoEmotions, EmoPillars, and SemEval-2018 Task-1C, which demonstrate consistent improvements and achieve state-of-the-art performance, highlighting the robustness and effectiveness of our solution. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we discuss some key prominent literature on the emotion recognition task. Section 3 introduces our proposed methodology, followed by our experiments in Section 4 and results in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6, we conclude our study.

2 Related Works

Early works have been mostly based on traditional machine learning algorithms- for example, SVM [15], Random Forest [16], and various ensemble learning approaches. The performance of such models depends heavily on the quality of manually engineered features, which typically involve techniques such as n-grams, TF-IDF [17], or specialized emotion-lexicon-based resources, for example WordNet-Affect [18], NRC [19], EmoSenticNet [20], and EmoLex [21]. However, these approaches are often inefficient and struggle to capture the deeper semantic meaning of language. With the advent of deep learning, the approach significantly changed from creating handcrafted features to automatic representation learning, using neural network

architectures like CNNs and RNNs. For instance, Hassan et al. [22] first demonstrated CNNs for sentence classification, while Polignano et al. [23] proposed a hybrid architecture composed of BiLSTM, CNN, and self-attention, achieving promising results in classification tasks. Recently, the emergence of diverse PLMs has reshaped the landscape and given rise to the finetuning paradigm, which has since been widely adopted. The top three models at the EmotionX 2019 challenge for emotion recognition in text are BERT-based models [24]. Then, Huang et al. [25] proposed a novel LSTM-based sequence-to-sequence architecture that leverages a bidirectional decoder to capture emotion correlations, outperforming the BERT-based model in multi-label emotion classification benchmarks. Fei et al. [26] introduced a network integrated with a variational autoencoder (VAE), enhanced with topic identification, for multi-label emotion detection. Gaonkar et al. [40] explicitly modeled label embeddings and their mutual correlations in emotion inference for ROC stories. Cortiz et al [27] and Sitoula et al [28] provided a clear comparison among different PLMs, showing RoBERTa consistently outperforms others on the GoEmotions dataset. Despite the rise of advanced reasoning LLMs (e.g., GPT4), these medium-sized models like RoBERTa remains a better option [29], [30]. However, data augmentation techniques using LLMs became a common practice for addressing the critical problem of class imbalance prevailing in these emotion datasets [31], [32]. Deng and Ren [33] adapted focal loss by adding a feature extraction and a correlation module. Cui et al. [34] introduced a loss function that uses class frequency to give more weight to underrepresented classes to improve their performance during training. Singh et al. [36] employ a multi-task framework that models the semantic meaning of emotion classes by predicting their definitions, using this as an auxiliary task to enhance emotion classification. Suresh and Ong [37] introduced Label-aware Contrastive Loss (LCL) to incorporate inter-class relationships, which help the model to differentiate between negative samples. This approach significantly improves performance, but can only be implemented in simple single-label classification tasks. Huang et al. [38] proposed the Asymmetric Polynomial Loss to improve the performance of underrepresented classes. Sui et al. [39] introduced a masked emotion modeling paradigm, inspired by masked language modeling, which encourages a Transformer to implicitly capture emotion correlations by predicting masked emotion states. Ramakrishnan and Babu [14] successfully adapted the Asymmetric function from computer vision, demonstrating its broader applicability and reported notable increases in the F1-score. Shvets

[35] developed a large synthetic dataset using LLM (EmoPillars) and performed transfer learning experiments, achieving SOTA on various datasets.

Although a lot of research has been done, the potential of contrastive frameworks adapted for fine-grained multi-label emotion classification, or joint optimization of multi-objective formulations, has remained largely unexplored. In this research, we explore these alternatives and present our approach in the following sections.

3 Methodology

In this section, we outline the methodological framework adopted in our study, detailing the datasets, model architectures, objective functions, and training protocols used throughout our experiments.

3.1 Datasets

We conducted extensive experiments across GoEmotions [41] and SemEval-2018 Task-1C [42] datasets to evaluate and validate the effectiveness of our approach. Additionally, we trained and tested our model on the EmoPillars dataset [35] to further assess its capability in large and diverse fine-grained emotion recognition tasks. Details about each dataset are given below.

3.1.1 GoEmotions

A large-scale multi-label emotion classification dataset, consisting of 58,000 English Reddit comments, manually annotated with 27 emotion categories plus a neutral label. It provides an ideal setting for multi-label emotion classification in fine-grained emotion recognition tasks. It poses several key challenges, such as high class imbalance and overlapping emotion categories with nuanced differences, making it a strong benchmark for evaluating emotion classification models. The dataset is diverse and representative of real-world emotional language, consisting of informal grammar, sarcasm, and ambiguous or context-dependent cues. We utilized the full GoEmotions taxonomy to train and evaluate our model performance. Figure 1 shows the emotion labels distribution, highlighting the class imbalance in the dataset.

3.1.2 EmoPillars

A massive synthetic dataset, developed to support both context-aware and context-less fine-grained emotion classification. The dataset has been created through a carefully designed LLM-based data synthesis pipeline, leveraging Mistral-7B-Instruct to generate emotionally

Figure 1: Emotion label distribution in GoEmotions.

rich and diverse comments grounded in narrative contexts. The dataset uses the same emotion taxonomy as GoEmotions but exhibits high complexity due to semantic diversity, rich topic coverage, and context personalization. We selected the context-less corpus consisting of 300K examples; however, only a preprocessed subset of 100K examples was used for training due to hardware constraints. In Figure 2, we highlight the class imbalance prevalent in the dataset.

Figure 2: Emotion label distribution in EmoPillars.

3.1.3 SemEval-2018 Task-1C

This is a part of the Affect in Tweets dataset, which includes tweets gathered between 2016 and 2017. The

dataset is a benchmark corpus designed to evaluate models’ ability to detect fine-grained emotions in short social media text. Although the dataset is also available in Arabic and Spanish, we restrict our experiments to the English subset only, comprising 10,983 tweets annotated with 11 distinct emotion categories. The dataset consists of real-world tweets and presents notable challenges due to non-standard grammar, misspellings, slang, and internet vernaculars. Many instances contain fragmented or context-dependent expressions in which emotional cues are implicit and require contextual influence. Table 1 shows some examples from this dataset. Moreover, the dataset also suffers from class imbalance, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Emotion label distribution in SemEval

3.2 Model Architecture

We investigate two model variants that share a common encoder backbone but differ in how they generate predictions and how their objective functions are formulated. Both architectures rely on the pretrained RoBERTa-base encoder to obtain contextualized representations of input text, and emotion label descriptions. The first variant is a classifier-head free architecture, where predictions are derived solely from the similarity between text embeddings and emotion-definition embeddings. The second variant introduces a lightweight classification head and is trained using a hybrid objective that combines similarity-based supervision with an auxiliary supervised loss.

3.2.1 RoBERTa Encoder

RoBERTa [8] (Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach) is a deep bidirectional transformer encoder that extends the BERT architecture through optimized pretraining strategies while preserving its core mathematical structure. Given an input token sequence $x = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$, RoBERTa first maps tokens to continuous representations by summing token embeddings, positional embeddings, and segment embed-

dings, producing an input matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$. This representation is processed through a stack of 12 transformer encoder layers, each consisting of multi-head self-attention and feed-forward networks. The self-attention mechanism computes contextualized representations as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

enabling each token to attend to all others in the sequence. Unlike BERT, RoBERTa removes the Next Sentence Prediction objective and is trained solely using dynamic Masked Language Modeling (MLM), where a subset of tokens is randomly masked, and the model maximizes the log-likelihood –

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}} \log p(w_i | x_{\setminus i})$$

RoBERTa further benefits from training on substantially larger corpora with increased batch sizes, longer sequences, and extended training schedules, resulting in more stable optimization and richer contextual representations. Owing to its optimized pretraining procedure and strong representational capacity, RoBERTa consistently demonstrates superior performance across a wide range of natural language understanding benchmarks than other models.

We obtain the sentence-level 768-dim vector representation of the input text by mean-pooling the final-layer hidden states and applying L2-normalization, which is then used for downstream objectives. The RoBERTa-base encoder model, consisting of a total of 125 parameters, is used in the backbone encoder for all our experiments, which is fine-tuned during training under the proposed learning objectives, allowing the model to adapt its representations to emotion-specific semantics while retaining the generalization capabilities.

3.2.2 Model I: Similarity-based Architecture

In the first setting, we adopt a formulation for fine-grained emotion classification, where emotion prediction is performed purely through semantic similarity in the embedding space, without introducing any task-specific classification head. The similarity-based architecture is just an encoder-centric design in which both input texts and emotion semantics are embedded into a shared representation space. This architecture is motivated by the observation that pretrained language models encode rich semantic information that can be exploited through representation learning, allowing emotion inference to be driven by relative similarity rather than direct categorical decision boundaries.

Let $x = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ denote an input text sequence consisting of n tokens, and let $\mathcal{E} = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_C\}$ represent the set of C emotion labels, where each emotion e_c is associated with a natural language definition describing its semantic meaning. Both the input text and the emotion definitions are processed using the same encoder $f_\theta(\cdot)$, parameterized by θ , ensuring that all representations are learned within a common semantic space.

For a given input text x , the encoder produces a sequence of contextualized token embeddings $H_x = [h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n]$, where each $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ corresponds to the hidden representation of token w_i in the final encoder layer. Let $m = (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_T)$, $m_t \in \{0, 1\}$ be the attention mask indicating valid (non-padding) tokens. To obtain a fixed-dimensional sentence-level representation, a mean pooling operation is applied across the token dimension:

$$\mathbf{z} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T m_t h_t}{\sum_{t=1}^T m_t}.$$

This operation ensures that only valid tokens contribute to the sentence representation, while padding tokens are effectively ignored. The resulting vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ serves as the global representation of the input text. To facilitate stable similarity computation and to emphasize angular relationships in the embedding space, this representation is further normalized using L2-normalization:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}} = \frac{\mathbf{z}}{\|\mathbf{z}\|_2}$$

Similarly, following the same logic as the input text, each emotion label definition associated with label e_c is tokenized and encoded using the same encoder $f_\theta(\cdot)$. The emotion definition embeddings are obtained, which are then subsequently normalized:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_c = \frac{\mathbf{e}_c}{\|\mathbf{e}_c\|_2}$$

where \mathbf{e}_c is the pooled vector representation of the emotion definition. By construction, both text representations $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ and emotion representations $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_c$ lie on the unit hypersphere in \mathbb{R}^d . This normalization ensures that similarity comparisons are governed purely by angular distance, reducing sensitivity to embedding magnitude and improving stability during optimization. Emotion prediction is performed by computing pairwise similarity scores between the input text embedding and each emotion embedding. Specifically, for a given text x and emotion e_c , a similarity score s_c is computed using the cosine similarity function:

$$\mathbf{s}_c = \cos(\tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_c) = \tilde{\mathbf{z}}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_c$$

This results in a similarity vector $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_C] \in \mathbb{R}^C$, where each component reflects the semantic alignment between the input text and a specific emotion definition. In the context of multi-label emotion classification, these similarity scores are interpreted independently for each emotion, enabling the model to assign multiple emotions to a single text instance without imposing mutual exclusivity constraints. The similarity scores are transformed using a sigmoid function to obtain probability estimates, which are subsequently thresholded to produce the final multi-label predictions.

Figure 4: Model I Similarity-based Architecture. The hashed boxes indicate emotion label definitions having high similarity scores with the text. All the scores are passed through sigmoid activation to get the probability scores, which are then thresholded to get the predictions

A key characteristic of this architecture is that emotion prediction is driven entirely by the learned geometry of the embedding space, rather than by a parametric classification layer. The encoder is encouraged to organize representations such that texts expressing a particular emotion are embedded closer to the corresponding emotion definition, while being pushed away from unrelated emotions. As a result, the model implicitly learns emotion-sensitive representations through similarity structure, allowing it to generalize across emotions and capture nuanced affective signals. Another important property of this design is that the emotion embeddings are not static prototypes; they are dynamically recomputed during training as the encoder parameters evolve. This coupling ensures that both text and emotion representations co-adapt throughout learning, leading to a shared embedding space that reflects both semantic meaning and emotional relevance. Moreover, because the architecture relies solely on a single shared encoder, it remains computationally efficient and avoids the parameter overhead introduced by additional classification layers or attention modules.

Overall, this similarity-based architecture reframes fine-grained emotion classification as a representation alignment problem, leveraging semantic label definitions and pretrained language representations to

achieve strong performance without explicit classifiers. This formulation not only provides an intuitive and interpretable modeling approach but also serves as a robust foundation upon which more expressive hybrid objectives can be introduced.

3.2.3 Model II: Classifier-based Architecture

The classifier-based hybrid model extends the similarity-driven formulation by incorporating an explicit prediction head while retaining the semantic structure induced by similarity learning. The motivation behind this is to preserve the representation-level alignment between textual inputs and emotion semantics, while simultaneously enabling a discriminative decision boundary that is better suited for fine-grained multi-label emotion classification. Importantly, this architecture is not introduced as a replacement for the similarity-based formulation, but rather as a complementary extension that leverages both representation learning and supervised classification signals within a unified framework.

At its core, this model also employs the same pretrained RoBERTa-base encoder as described previously. Given an input text sequence $x = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$, the encoder produces contextualized embedding representations of 768 dimensions through stacked 12 multi-head self-attention and feed-forward layers. As in the previous formulation, the final hidden states are aggregated using the mean pooling, followed by L2-normalization, yielding a fixed-dimensional sentence representation $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$. This normalized representation serves as the shared semantic embedding upon which both similarity-based alignment and classification-based prediction are performed. In parallel, emotion descriptions corresponding to each label are also processed through the same encoder, ensuring that both text inputs and emotion semantics are embedded in a common latent space. This shared embedding space is critical to maintaining semantic coherence across objectives, as it enforces that representations learned for classification remain grounded in the meaning of emotion labels rather than arbitrary decision boundaries. Unlike architectures that introduce task-specific encoders or cross-attention mechanisms, our proposed model relies on a single encoder to preserve parameter efficiency and training stability under limited computational resources. On top of the encoder, a lightweight classifier head is added to enable direct multi-label prediction. This classifier is implemented as a linear projection that maps the embedding \mathbf{t} to a vector of logits $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^C$, where C denotes the number of emotion categories. Formally, this can

be expressed as

$$\mathbf{h} = W.t + b,$$

where $W \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times d}$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}^C$ are learnable parameters. The classifier head consists of a dense layer of 512 units, activated by the GELU activation function, with layer normalization and dropout added to avoid overfitting, and to ensure that the primary representational capacity remains within the encoder itself. Crucially, the introduction of the classifier head does not alter the role of the similarity-based representation. Instead, the same normalized text embeddings used for classification are also employed to compute similarity scores against emotion embeddings. As a result, the model is simultaneously encouraged to organize the embedding space according to semantic similarity while also learning label-specific discriminative cues through supervised signals. This dual usage of the text representation ensures that the classifier operates on embeddings that are semantically structured rather than purely optimized for classification accuracy. Thus, the classifier-based model architecture represents a principled extension of the similarity-driven model. It maintains the strengths of semantic alignment through shared embeddings while introducing a minimal yet effective classification module that improves predictive performance. This architectural design enables the model to achieve state-of-the-art results using a base encoder model, demonstrating that carefully structured objectives can be more impactful than architectural complexity alone.

Figure 5: Model II Classifier-based Architecture

3.3 Objective Functions

Objective functions (also called loss functions or cost functions) are mathematical formulations that quantify how well a model’s predictions align with the desired targets, shaping the representational space induced by the model and directly influencing its ability to capture fine-grained emotional semantics. Formally, given a model parameterized by θ , the training process aims to

solve an optimization problem of the form

$$\theta^* = \arg \min \theta \mathcal{L}(y, f(x; \theta))$$

where $\mathcal{L}(\cdot)$ denotes the objective function, $f(x; \theta)$ represents the model’s output for input x and y represents the ground-truth value.

In this work, we investigate two complementary training objectives designed to exploit semantic similarity between textual inputs and emotion definitions while addressing the challenges of multi-label emotion classification. First, we employ a similarity-driven objective using our proposed NT-BiXent loss, which encourages the model to maximize alignment between a text representation and its corresponding emotion representations, without relying on an explicit classifier. Second, we extend this formulation with a hybrid objective that integrates the similarity-based loss with a classification-oriented loss to further enhance discriminative capacity, particularly for imbalanced emotion distributions. The following subsections describe these objectives in detail.

3.3.1 NT-BiXent Loss

To enable classifier-free emotion prediction through semantic similarity, we formulate a similarity-based learning objective- NT-BiXent (Normalized Temperature-scaled Binary Cross-Entropy) that combines the principles of contrastive learning with multi-label binary supervision. Contrastive learning has emerged as a powerful paradigm for representation learning, particularly in settings where explicit supervision is scarce or weakly structured. At its core, contrastive learning aims to structure the representation space by bringing semantically related instances closer while pushing unrelated instances apart, typically through a similarity-based objective. Among the most influential formulations in this family is the Normalized Temperature-scaled Cross-Entropy (NT-Xent) loss [43], which has been widely adopted in self-supervised and supervised contrastive learning frameworks.

Let $\mathcal{D} = x_{i=1}^N$ denote a batch of input samples. In the NT-Xent framework, each sample is associated with a positive counterpart (e.g., an augmented view of the same instance), while all remaining samples in the batch act as negatives. Given an encoder $f(\cdot)$, each input is mapped to a representation $z_i = f(x_i) \in \mathbb{R}^d$, which is typically L2-normalized such that $\|z_i\|_2 = 1$. The cosine similarity between two representations z_i and z_j is defined as

$$\text{sim}(z_i, z_j) = \frac{z_i^\top z_j}{\|z_i\|_2 \|z_j\|_2}$$

The NT-Xent loss for a positive pair (i, j) is then given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-Xent}}(i, j) = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_k)/\tau)}$$

where $\tau > 0$ is a temperature parameter that controls the sharpness of the similarity distribution. This formulation can be interpreted as a softmax-based classification objective, where each anchor representation z_i is encouraged to identify its positive counterpart among a set of negatives correctly. The temperature parameter plays a crucial role in scaling the logits: smaller values of τ amplify similarity differences, leading to sharper decision boundaries in the embedding space. While NT-Xent loss variants [37] have proven highly effective in single-positive, single-label classification settings, they exhibit inherent structural limitations when applied directly to multi-label problems, such as fine-grained emotion classification. Our objective NT-BiXent is explicitly designed for multi-label emotion classification settings, by replacing softmax normalization with independent binary decisions using BCE.

Let x denote an input text sequence and let $\mathcal{E} = e_1, e_2, \dots, e_C$ denote the set of emotion label descriptions, where C is the total number of emotion categories. Both the input text and the emotion descriptions are encoded using the same pretrained transformer encoder $f_\theta(\cdot)$, yielding a shared embedding space. Specifically, the sentence-level representation of the input text is given by:

$$z = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i} \sum_{i=1}^n m_i h_i, \quad z \leftarrow \frac{z}{\|z\|_2}$$

where h_i denotes the contextualized token representations from the final encoder layer, and $m_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the attention mask. The resulting vector is L2-normalized to constrain representations to the unit hypersphere. Similarly, each emotion description e_c is encoded to obtain a corresponding normalized emotion embedding

$$e_c = \frac{f_\theta(e_c)}{\|f_\theta(e_c)\|_2}, \quad c = 1, \dots, C.$$

Given the normalized text embedding z and a set of normalized emotion embeddings, we compute temperature-scaled similarity scores between the text and each emotion as

$$s = \frac{1}{\tau} \{ \langle z, e \mid e \in \mathcal{E}, \rangle \} \in \mathcal{R}^C$$

where $\tau > 0$ is a temperature parameter that rescales cosine similarities so that the loss becomes more sensitive to angular differences between text and emotion

embeddings. This encourages clearer separation in embedding space while preserving stable multi-label optimization. Without this temperature scaling, the gradients are weak, resulting in slow and unstable training. Also, the model under-separates positive and negative emotions, showing poor performance results at testing, while trained in similar settings.

Unlike NT-Xent, which applies a softmax over similarities and assumes a single positive per instance, we treat each emotion category as an independent binary decision. Let $y \in \{0, 1\}^C$ denote the multi-hot ground-truth emotion label vector for the input text. The similarity scores are optimized using a binary cross-entropy objective applied directly to the temperature-scaled cosine similarities:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-BiXent}} = - \sum_{c=1}^C \left[y_c \log \sigma(s_c) + (1 - y_c) \log (1 - \sigma(s_c)) \right]$$

where $s_c = \frac{1}{\tau} \langle z, e \rangle$ denote the c -th component of the similarity vector and $\sigma(\cdot)$ denotes the sigmoid function. The above formula is our proposed NT-BiXent objective function (or loss function), which can be interpreted as a multi-label extension of normalized temperature-scaled contrastive learning, where positive text–emotion pairs are explicitly pulled together in the embedding space, while negative pairs are pushed apart. The use of L2 normalization ensures that optimization is based on angular similarity, while temperature scaling modulates gradient magnitude and separation strength between positive and negative pairs. Our first model variant, Model I, has been trained solely relying on NT-BiXent Loss, and later we developed a hybrid objective combining our loss with Clipped Asymmetric Loss [14], which is used to train our second model, Model II.

3.3.2 Clipped Asymmetric Loss

Multi-label emotion classification presents inherent challenges arising from severe class imbalance and label sparsity prevalent in these datasets. In this setting, a single textual instance may simultaneously express multiple emotions, while the absence of an emotion is treated as an equally important prediction outcome. Consequently, for a problem with C emotion categories, each instance induces C independent binary classification decisions. However, only a small subset of these labels is typically active for any given instance, leading to a strong dominance of negative labels during training. This imbalance causes conventional loss functions, such as Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE), to be

overwhelmed by easy negative samples, resulting in biased optimization dynamics and degraded performance on minority emotion classes.

Formally, let the dataset consist of N samples $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$, each annotated with a multi-hot label vector

$$y_i = (y_{i1}, y_{i2}, \dots, y_{iC}), \quad y_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$$

where $y_{ij} = 1$ indicates the presence of the j -th emotion in the i -th sample. A transformer-based encoder produces a corresponding vector of logits $\mathbf{z}_i = (z_{i1}, z_{i2}, \dots, z_{iC})$ which are independently mapped to probabilities via the sigmoid activation:

$$p_{ij} = \sigma(z_{ij}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z_{ij}}}$$

These probabilities represent the model’s confidence that a given emotion label applies to the input text.

In standard multi-label settings, these probabilities are directly optimized using a BCE objective, which implicitly assumes balanced label distributions and equal importance of positive and negative samples. Such assumptions do not hold in emotion recognition, where negative labels vastly outnumber positives and contribute limited semantic information. As a result, BCE-based optimization is dominated by trivial negatives, suppressing gradient signals for rare but informative emotion categories. An additional practical concern during training is numerical stability. As the model becomes increasingly confident, the predicted probabilities may approach extreme values, close to 0 or 1. This can lead to unstable gradients or undefined logarithmic terms. To address this issue, the Clipped Asymmetric Loss (CAL) introduces explicit probability clipping:

$$\hat{p}_{ij} = \text{clip}(p_{ij}, \varepsilon, 1 - \varepsilon)$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a small constant. This clipping ensures numerical robustness and prevents excessive gradient magnitudes, while also acting as a form of implicit regularization by discouraging overconfident predictions, particularly beneficial in the presence of noisy or ambiguous emotion labels.

The core principle of CAL lies in its asymmetric treatment of positive and negative labels. Instead of employing a single symmetric loss formulation, CAL decomposes the total loss into distinct positive and negative components, allowing fine-grained control over their respective contributions. For positive labels ($y_{ij} = 1$), the loss component is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ij}^{\text{pos}} = -y_{ij} \log(\hat{p}_{ij})(1 - \hat{p}_{ij})^{\gamma_{\text{pos}}}$$

where $\gamma_{\text{pos}} \geq 0$ is the positive focusing parameter. The logarithmic term penalizes low-confidence predictions

for true emotion labels, while the modulating factor $(1 - \hat{p}_{ij})^{\gamma_{\text{pos}}}$ down-weights easy positives that are already well classified and amplifies gradients for hard positives. This mechanism directs learning toward underrepresented and difficult emotion categories. For negative labels ($y_{ij} = 0$), the loss component is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ij}^{\text{neg}} = -(1 - y_{ij}) \log(1 - \hat{p}_{ij})(\hat{p}_{ij})^{\gamma_{\text{neg}}}$$

where $\gamma_{\text{neg}} \geq 0$ is the negative focusing parameter. This term penalizes false positive predictions, i.e., cases where the model assigns high probability to emotions that are not present. The modulating factor $(\hat{p}_{ij})^{\gamma_{\text{neg}}}$ suppresses the contribution of easy negative labels that are correctly predicted with very low probability, thereby preventing them from dominating the optimization process.

The total loss for a single training instance is obtained by aggregating the positive and negative components across all emotion labels

$$\mathcal{L}_i = \sum_{j=1}^C (\mathcal{L}_{ij}^{\text{pos}} + \mathcal{L}_{ij}^{\text{neg}})$$

The overall training objective is then defined as the average loss over the dataset:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{L}_i$$

From a broader perspective, CAL can be viewed as a generalization of loss functions designed for imbalanced learning. Binary Cross-Entropy treats all samples uniformly and fails to distinguish between easy and hard examples, while Focal Loss introduces a focusing mechanism but applies it symmetrically to both positive and negative samples. CAL extends these ideas by employing separate focusing parameters for positives and negatives, offering finer control over the learning dynamics. The explicit clipping mechanism further distinguishes CAL by ensuring stable and consistent gradient behavior throughout training.

3.3.3 Hybrid Objective

While the normalized temperature-scaled binary cross-entropy-based similarity objective (NT-BiXent) effectively enforces semantic alignment between textual representations and emotion definitions, it optimizes the model purely from a representation learning perspective. In particular, this objective encourages the encoder to structure the embedding space such that texts expressing a given emotion are geometrically closer to the corresponding emotion representations than to

irrelevant emotions. As demonstrated in our experiments, this similarity-driven formulation alone already yields strong performance and outperforms several competitive baseline models.

However, similarity-based learning alone does not explicitly optimize for the final decision boundaries required for multi-label emotion classification. In practical emotion recognition settings, performance is evaluated based on discrete label predictions derived from thresholded probability scores, and thus depends not only on the relative ordering of similarity scores but also on their absolute calibration across emotion categories. This motivates the incorporation of an additional objective that directly supervises the classification behavior of the model at the label level. Therefore, we introduce a hybrid training objective that jointly optimizes the similarity-based NT-BiXent loss and the Clipped Asymmetric Loss. The hybrid formulation leverages the complementary strengths of the two objectives. The NT-BiXent component acts as a semantic regularizer, shaping the shared encoder to produce emotion-aware representations by aligning texts with their corresponding emotion definitions in the embedding space. In contrast, the CAL component explicitly optimizes label-wise prediction confidence, addressing the extreme class imbalance inherent to fine-grained emotion datasets and improving discrimination among rare emotions.

Formally, let $\mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-BiXent}}$ denote the NT-BiXent loss defined over text-emotion similarity scores, and let \mathcal{L}_{CAL} denote the Clipped Asymmetric Loss computed over the classifier outputs. The overall hybrid objective is defined as a weighted combination of the two losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{hybrid}} = \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-BiXent}} + (1 - \lambda) \mathcal{L}_{\text{CAL}}$$

where $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is a hyperparameter controlling the relative contribution of the similarity-based and classification-based objectives.

This joint optimization strategy enables the model to learn emotion-discriminative representations while simultaneously refining label-specific decision boundaries. Importantly, both loss terms are optimized over a shared encoder, allowing gradients from semantic similarity learning and asymmetric classification supervision to interact during training. As a result, the encoder learns representations that are not only semantically grounded in emotion definitions but also well-calibrated for multi-label prediction under severe class imbalance. In our experiments, we find that this hybrid objective consistently improves macro-level evaluation metrics over the similarity-only formulation, achieving state-of-the-art performance while maintaining a lightweight architecture and modest computational requirements. This demonstrates that combining dual

objectives - representation-level alignment with label-aware asymmetric supervision provides a principled and effective training paradigm for fine-grained emotion classification.

4 Experiment Setup

In this section, we describe the experimental setup used to evaluate the proposed models. We detail the data preprocessing pipeline, training configurations, evaluation metrics, and baseline models used for comparison. All experiments are conducted consistently across datasets to ensure fair and reproducible evaluation.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

We employ a unified preprocessing strategy to standardize the input space across datasets, suppress non-semantic variability, and align the resulting text distribution with the assumptions of pretrained transformer encoders. All preprocessing operations are applied before tokenization and model inference and are shared across datasets. Input text is first normalized through Unicode standardization and transcoded into strict ASCII format to remove malformed characters and rare symbols that unnecessarily fragment the embedding space. Non-semantic tokens, including emojis and URLs, are excluded to reduce vocabulary sparsity. Symbol filtering is performed in a context-aware manner; currency symbols are retained only when directly associated with numerical values to preserve quantitative context, while isolated symbols are removed. Irregular whitespace is normalized to ensure consistent token boundaries. Emotion recognition is formulated as a multi-label classification problem, with target labels encoded as multi-hot binary vectors. GoEmotions and EmoPillars labels are represented using 28-dimensional vectors, while SemEval-2018 labels are encoded as 11-dimensional vectors reflecting their dataset-specific taxonomy.

4.2 Data Splits and Statistics

The GoEmotions, Emopillars, and SemEval-2018 Task-1C datasets were split into training, validation, and test sets, according to the ratios suggested by their respective authors. For the GoEmotions dataset, approximately 75% of the data was allocated to training, while 9.4% was assigned to each of the validation and test sets. This split provides sufficient data for fine-grained emotion classification and maintains balanced subsets for hyperparameter tuning and model evaluation [41]. For the EmoPillars dataset, about 61% of the data was used for training, with 19.5% allocated

to each of the validation and test sets. The SemEval-2018 Task 1C dataset was partitioned with 62% of the data assigned to training, 8% to validation, and 30% to testing [42]. This ensures sufficient training data while retaining a large test set for evaluating the model on unseen data.

Dataset	Train	Val	Test	Total
GoEmotions	43410	5426	5427	58000
SemEval-18 Task-1C	6838	886	3259	10983
EmoPillars	99999	32010	32071	164080

TABLE II: *GoEmotions, SemEval-2018, and EmoPillars datasets summary*

4.3 Training and Hyperparameter Settings

The proposed model was implemented using PyTorch, leveraging the Hugging Face Transformers library for loading the pre-trained RoBERTa encoder and tokenization. All experiments were conducted in the Google Colab environment, using T4 GPU. The AdamW optimizer with separate learning rates for the encoder and the classifier layer was used in conjunction with a cosine learning rate scheduler with warmup. A batch size of 64 was used for training models on all the datasets. For training our similarity-based model architecture, i.e., Model I, the temperature parameter in the NT-BiXent was experimented with a range of values from 0.01 to 0.07, and the best result was obtained with a temperature of 0.01. However, decreasing the temperature value further causes the exploding gradients problem. For training our second model variant, i.e., Model II, using the hybrid objective, a temperature value of 0.05 produced the best result. The validation macro-F1 score was chosen as the primary performance monitoring metric. Mixed-precision training was employed to improve computational efficiency, along with gradient accumulation to simulate larger effective batch sizes. Table III summarizes the hyperparameter settings that produced the best results.

Parameter	GoEmotions	SemEval-18	EmoPillars
encoder lr-rate	2.5e-5	2e-5	2.5e-5
classifier lr-rate	1.5e-4	1.5e-4	1.5e-4
weight decay	0.001	0.01	0.001
warmup ratio	0.1	0.08	0.1
temperature	0.05	0.05	0.05
γ_{pos}	1	1	1
γ_{neg}	3	4	3
clipping constant	0.04	0.05	0.04
epochs	10	10	8

TABLE III: *Hyperparameter settings*

5 Experiment Results

In this section, we present a comprehensive evaluation of our proposed approaches by highlighting our experiment results obtained and analyze the impact of our objective functions. We report results for both variants of our model: (i) Model I: similarity-based model, and (ii) Model II: trained with the hybrid objective.

5.1 Performance on GoEmotions Dataset

We conduct extensive experiments using both model architectures on the GoEmotions dataset. We also did various counter experiments using the known standard approaches and evaluated them on the test set, to validate the robustness of our approaches. Table IV highlights the detailed performance results of the different experiments we performed. Our classifier-free model – Model I, trained using the contrastive semantic-similarity-based approach with the proposed NT-Xent objective, achieves a significantly high macro-F1 score of 0.54, outperforming existing strong baseline models in the GoEmotions benchmarks. However, the best results are obtained by the second model- Model II, which is trained using the proposed hybrid dual objective function. Table V shows the performance comparisons among the different benchmark models, where we find that both of our model achieves competitive performance, while the latter achieves state-of-the-art results in the fine-grained multi-label emotion classification task.

Objective Variant	Macro F1
Using only BCE loss	0.45
Using only Clipped Asymmetric loss	0.53
Using proposed NT-BiXent loss	0.54
Using proposed hybrid objective	0.56

TABLE IV: Comparison of Macro-F1 scores obtained using different training objective variants.

Figure 6: Model's performance comparison on the GoEmotions dataset

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Macro
GPT-4 [31]	0.10	0.17	0.13
BERT-base [41]	0.40	0.63	0.46
Seq2Emo [25]	-	-	0.47
BERT-base [30]	-	-	0.48
RoBERTa-base [27]	-	-	0.49
RoBERTa-base ^{GPT-3.5} [31]	-	-	0.51
BERT-base ^{BART} [32]	0.52	0.53	0.52
BERT-base [36]	0.55	0.54	0.52
BERT-base [14]	0.54	0.56	0.54
RoBERTa-base (Model I) [ours]	0.53	0.57	0.54
π^{emo} -RoBERTa-large [35]	0.58	0.58	0.55
RoBERTa-base (Model II) [ours]	0.57	0.57	0.56

TABLE V: Comparative results of model performance on the GoEmotions benchmark.

Figure 7: Quadrant analysis of emotion-wise performance of Model II on the GoEmotions dataset. Emotions are plotted by F1-score against label frequency (log scale) and colored by difficulty category based on median thresholds-highlighting hard, robust, weak, and easy emotions.

Figure 8: Emotion frequency vs F1-scores: GoEmotions

5.2 Performance on SemEval-2018 Task-1C Dataset

Following the setup used for the GoEmotions dataset, we trained our model variants with our proposed approaches on the SemEval-18 Task 1C dataset. The similarity-based model (Model I) achieves competitive performance with a macro F1 score of 0.57, while the second variant (Model II) yields further improvements, attaining a macro F1 score of 0.61 and establishing state-of-the-art results in this task. Table VI presents a comparison of the performances of different models on the dataset.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Macro
Dep-GAT [44]	0.62	0.68	0.52
TCS Research [48]	-	-	0.53
BERT+DK [45]	-	-	0.55
BERT+GCN [46]	-	-	0.56
RoBERTa-base (Model I) [ours]	0.55	0.59	0.57
SpanEmo [47]	-	-	0.58
BERT-base [14]	0.67	0.54	0.59
UCCA-GAT [44]	0.62	0.66	0.60
RoBERTa-base (Model II) [ours]	0.54	0.70	0.61

TABLE VI: Comparison of model performance on the SemEval-2018 Task-1C benchmark

Figure 9: Comparison of F1-scores across emotions for the proposed and baseline models on the SemEval-18 dataset.

Figure 10: Emotion frequency vs F1-scores: SemEval

5.3 Performance on EmoPillars Dataset

Our approaches were further tested on the EmoPillars dataset. Standard fine-tuning with BCE loss yields a macro F1 score of 0.67, while our classifier-free, similarity-based approach improves performance to 0.69. Model II performs best overall, achieving a macro F1 score of 0.70. As the EmoPillars dataset has been introduced only recently, existing benchmark results are limited. Consequently, we establish the first systematic evaluation on this dataset using base encoder variants. Within this controlled setting, Model II achieves the strongest performance among all traditional baseline models, providing a new reference benchmark for future work. Table VII shows the per-label performance metrics of Model II on the EmoPillars dataset.

Figure 11: Emotion frequency vs F1-scores: EmoPillars

Figure 12: Emotion frequency vs F1-scores: EmoPillars

Figure 13: Comparison of F1-scores across emotions for the proposed and baseline models on the EmoPillars dataset.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Macro
admiration	0.72	0.78	0.75
amusement	0.88	0.59	0.70
anger	0.84	0.90	0.87
annoyance	0.78	0.83	0.80
approval	0.51	0.39	0.44
caring	0.65	0.68	0.67
confusion	0.77	0.81	0.79
curiosity	0.88	0.82	0.85
desire	0.81	0.81	0.81
disappointment	0.78	0.87	0.82
disapproval	0.61	0.38	0.47
disgust	0.81	0.74	0.77
embarrassment	0.76	0.22	0.34
excitement	0.72	0.77	0.75
fear	0.89	0.79	0.84
gratitude	0.89	0.70	0.79
grief	0.73	0.76	0.74
joy	0.73	0.77	0.75
love	0.83	0.59	0.69
nervousness	0.80	0.82	0.81
optimism	0.82	0.78	0.80
pride	0.86	0.86	0.86
realization	0.96	0.07	0.13
relief	0.80	0.62	0.70
remorse	0.59	0.34	0.43
sadness	0.74	0.81	0.78
surprise	0.82	0.81	0.81
neutral	0.79	0.62	0.70
Micro avg	0.79	0.77	0.78
Macro avg	0.78	0.68	0.70
Weighted avg	0.79	0.77	0.77

TABLE VII: Per-label performance metrics on of the proposed model (Model II) on the EmoPillars dataset.

6 Limitations and Future Directions

Despite the observed improvements, challenges persist, notably limited performance on extremely rare emotion classes caused by data sparsity. Addressing this limitation may require investigation of data augmentation techniques, such as prompt-based text augmentation. Our approaches rely on predefined emotion categories; therefore, the use of well-defined labels is crucial for achieving improved performance. Also, our models do not consider multilingual data, restricting applicability in global contexts. Future work could focus on adapting the framework to handle multilingual datasets. The high computational requirement of the model, particularly for large datasets such as EmoPillars, is a challenge for scalability. Techniques such as model pruning and knowledge distillation offer promising avenues for improving model efficiency.

7 Conclusion

In this work, we presented a novel perspective on fine-grained emotion classification by reframing the task through the lens of similarity-based representation learning and dual-objective optimization. Departing from conventional classifier-centric paradigms, we first demonstrated that a transformer-based encoder trained solely via similarity-driven objective using our proposed NT-BiXent loss, leveraging semantic emotion definitions and contrastive learning, which achieves competitive performance and outperforms several established baselines. This finding highlights that meaningful emotion discrimination can be effectively learned at the representation level, without reliance on task-specific classifier heads. Building upon this insight, we further introduced a hybrid training strategy that jointly optimizes a similarity-based objective and a classification-oriented loss tailored for imbalanced multi-label settings. By combining the strengths of our contrastive semantic alignment objective NT-BiXent and Clipped Asymmetric Loss, the proposed hybrid model consistently achieved superior performance across multiple benchmarks, attaining state-of-the-art results while remaining computationally efficient. Extensive experiments were conducted across multiple datasets to validate the robustness of our framework and confirm the complementary nature of the two objectives. Overall, this work contributes a unified and efficient framework for fine-grained emotion classification that bridges similarity-based representation learning and supervised multi-label optimization.

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A Emotion Category Definitions

Admiration: respect and high regard for something excellent or skilled.

Amusement: feeling great happiness and overwhelming delight.

Anger: strong feeling of displeasure and hostility or tension.

Annoyance: mild irritation or impatience for disturbance or distraction.

Anticipation: eager expectation or readiness for something that might happen.

Approval: favorable opinion, agreement with something.

Caring: showing concern, kindness for others well-being.

Confusion: lacking understanding, unsure or uncertain.

Curiosity: strong feeling to know or learn something.

Desire: strong feeling of wanting or wishing for something.

Disappointment: displeasure due to unfulfilled expectations.

Disapproval: unfavorable opinion or negative judgment.

Disgust: feeling of revulsion or strong sickness due to some offensive.

Embarrassment: awkward feeling, or shame in public.

Excitement: intense enthusiasm, thrilled, energetic.

Fear: acute alarm caused by perceived danger or threat.

Gratitude: thankfulness and appreciation for kindness.

Grief: deep sorrow, emotional pain caused by loss or death.

Joy: finding something funny, lighthearted and entertaining.

Love: deep affection or attraction, profound connection.

Nervousness: feeling uneasy, worried or apprehensive about something.

Optimism: hopefulness and confidence about something in future.

Pessimism: expecting negative or unfavorable outcomes.

Pride: satisfied with one’s achievement or high standards.

Realization: suddenly achieving clear understanding, awareness.

Relief: feeling of release from anxiety, pain or distress.

Remorse: deep regret or guilt for committed wrong doing.

Sadness: unhappy, sorrowful and lacking cheerful-

ness.

Surprise: an unexpected, startled feeling from something sudden.

Trust: confidence in someone’s reliability, honesty or good intentions.

Neutral: absence of strong emotion, neither positive or negative.

B Per-Class Macro-F1 Comparison

B.1 GoEmotions

Emotion	BERT [41]	RoBERTa-large [35]	Model I	Model II
admiration	0.65	0.71	0.69	0.70
amusement	0.80	0.83	0.82	0.81
anger	0.47	0.53	0.51	0.51
annoyance	0.34	0.38	0.38	0.38
approval	0.36	0.42	0.42	0.43
caring	0.39	0.44	0.44	0.46
confusion	0.37	0.46	0.45	0.48
curiosity	0.54	0.57	0.55	0.58
desire	0.49	0.53	0.50	0.57
disappointment	0.28	0.36	0.32	0.30
disapproval	0.39	0.46	0.42	0.38
disgust	0.45	0.48	0.50	0.50
embarrassment	0.43	0.50	0.47	0.54
excitement	0.34	0.47	0.43	0.44
fear	0.60	0.65	0.66	0.66
gratitude	0.86	0.91	0.91	0.91
grief	0.00	0.57	0.60	0.67
joy	0.51	0.64	0.61	0.63
love	0.78	0.82	0.78	0.80
nervousness	0.35	0.46	0.47	0.39
neutral	0.68	0.58	0.66	0.69
optimism	0.51	0.53	0.55	0.56
pride	0.36	0.28	0.48	0.52
realization	0.21	0.19	0.23	0.29
relief	0.15	0.67	0.48	0.57
remorse	0.66	0.58	0.68	0.69
sadness	0.49	0.57	0.57	0.58
surprise	0.50	0.68	0.57	0.58
Micro avg.	–	0.61	0.59	0.62
Macro avg.	0.46	0.55	0.54	0.56

TABLE VIII: Per-emotion macro-F1 scores on the GoEmotions dataset. Model I and Model II denote our proposed RoBERTa-base variants.

B.2 SemEval-2018 Task-1C

Emotion	Dep-GAT [44]	UCCA-GAT [44]	Model I	Model II
anger	0.74	0.83	0.78	0.79
anticipation	0.36	0.45	0.43	0.40
disgust	0.81	0.81	0.77	0.76
fear	0.41	0.45	0.43	0.74
joy	0.73	0.84	0.80	0.85
love	0.60	0.61	0.58	0.64
optimism	0.72	0.76	0.72	0.76
pessimism	0.66	0.69	0.66	0.45
sadness	0.68	0.75	0.69	0.71
surprise	0.32	0.24	0.24	0.33
trust	0.31	0.16	0.15	0.22
Micro avg.	0.64	0.66	0.63	0.71
Macro avg.	0.58	0.60	0.57	0.61

TABLE IX: Per-emotion macro-F1 scores on the SemEval-2018 Task-1C dataset.

C Discussion

The notable observation from our experiments is that the similarity-based training objective alone, without an explicit classifier head, using our NT-BiXent loss function, yields competitive performance and consistently outperforms traditional classifier-based models trained using the standard BCE loss, in fine-grained multi-label classification task. This suggests that emotion recognition can be effectively framed as a semantic matching problem between text representations and emotion descriptions, rather than relying solely on direct classification. The results indicate that pretrained language models already encode rich affective information, which can be exploited through appropriately designed similarity objectives. We further observed that augmenting the similarity-based objective with a classification-oriented loss, especially Asymmetric Loss variant, leads to additional performance gains, particularly in macro-level evaluation metrics. This highlights the complementary nature of the dual objectives: while the similarity-based loss encourages semantically structured representations, the classification loss sharpens decision boundaries for individual emotion categories.

We note that temperature scaling plays a critical role during training by controlling the sharpness of similarity scores before they are passed to the sigmoid function. Although varying the temperature at inference time has minimal impact on final predictions, appropriate temperature selection during training significantly affects convergence behavior and representation quality. Empirically, we found lower temperature values to be more effective, likely due to their ability to amplify informative gradients for hard positive and negative emotion pairs. The decision threshold is set to the standard value of 0.5.

While a recent work [49] reports a notably high macro-F1 score of 0.58 on the GoEmotions benchmark, closer inspection reveals certain inconsistencies that complicate direct comparison. In particular, citing baseline results that do not align with the original values reported by the respective authors— for example, Ramakrishnan et al. [14] reported their best macro-F1 0.54, whereas the subsequent work report an improved macro-F1 of 0.56 without clarifying changes in any configuration, evaluation protocol, or decision threshold. Additionally, there are cases where comparisons are made between models trained and evaluated on different label configurations (e.g., 18-label versus the 28-label setting), which inherently alter task difficulty and render such comparisons methodologically unreliable. Furthermore, the lack

of publicly released code, pretrained checkpoints, and detailed evaluation procedures (including thresholding strategies for multi-label prediction) limits the ability to independently verify or reproduce these reported results. In contrast, our work emphasizes transparency and reproducibility: all source code, training configurations, evaluation scripts, and pretrained models are publicly released via GitHub and Huggingface. Under this fully open and verifiable setting, our model has been established to outperform baselines and represents state-of-the-art performance among reproducible, and open-source models.

GitHub: [Hidden-States-AI-Labs/EmoAxis](#)

Huggingface: [Hidden States AI Labs](#)